

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

CLEAN NANOENERGY AND NANOTECHNOLOGIES OF THE NEW TECHNOLOGICAL ORDER CREATE A CLEAN CLIMATE ON PLANET EARTH

Kulakov A.

*Korresponding Member of the Russian Academy of Sciences,
now the Institute of Functional Economic Systems. Moscow. Russia. Ph.D. (phys.math.)
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Choose the most difficult path. But on it you will not meet competitors

Charles de Gaulle

In the world there is a community more terrible than the bandit community of scientists

Niels Bohr

Abstract

Very high cost of energy when using existing industrial technologies resources remain, due to their imperfection and the need to heat almost all fixed assets, as well as the lack of resources to restore the disturbed balance between the biosphere and the technosphere, caused by the lack of highly efficient cycle technologies: mining, production of useful products from them, rational use of these products and finally, their disposal. Of what is mined from the ground, 95% is either used for intermediate consumption or buried. The world is in a state where the environmental damage of technology has exceeded the capabilities of the Earth. With the preservation of existing industrial technologies, resources in the world are becoming less and less, humanity has nothing to pay for cleaning up and restoring the environment. Only new technologies and new resources will save humanity from collapse. The solution lies in the search for a new alternative, renewable, harmless and sustainable source of energy, the very use of which is an industry for the processing and destruction of generated waste - recycling, comparable in volume to the entire transport and energy complex. In this case, it is possible to stabilize the world at the current level of consumption and implement the idea of sustainable development.

This article, founded on in results from fifty years from author's work on development from break through energy technologies in The theory and practice of non-ideal, close to non-degenerate plasma began with the candidate of physical and mathematical sciences A.A. Rumyantsev, who, unfortunately, passed away in 1990. The author predicted and confirmed the existence of a fundamentally new state from physical matter - quantum plasma nanocondensate - liquefied plasma, an association in specifications inherent in standard liquid and ionized plasma - a fundamentally new, efficient and harmless source of energy, the use of which makes it possible to reduce environmental pollution with waste. Cleaning up the planet Earth polluted to the limit, in some areas of which gas contamination, slagging, municipal waste exceed all permissible standards, will lead to an increase in immune system in Population, and for the first time in the world, it led to the creation of a clean climate without pollution by human waste products and, of course, the stabilization of the world for which I will do This possible behind people to exist safely.

Keywords: Non-ideal quantum plasma, Modern energy, Mechanism of energy release, New state of matter - quantum plasma condensate, Alternative, clean, natural, efficient, renewable and stable fundamentally new source of energy, Plasma combustion of fuels, Purification of the planet's ecosphere.

I express my gratitude to scientists from eight-seven countries of the world for their interest in my work, who confirmed the world significance and value for mankind for the fact that mankind for the first time created a source of nature-like and clean energy - Nanoenergy, the way of life of the New Technologist. The nomenclature of my scientific works has increased significantly, and even their enumeration, and even more so a brief description, would require the volume of a brief reference book. Therefore, on the advice of my colleagues, I wrote an extremely concise and extremely understandable presentation of the essence of Nanoenergy of the New Technological Way for a wide range of researchers - physicists, chemists, power engineers, materials scientists, farmers, climatologists, hydrologists, soil scientists, accompanied by a physical and technological interpretation of the processes under consideration. As for the mathematical side, it is set out

in the list of attached literature. Considering the ratio of mathematical and special technical education, A. Poincaré wrote the following: An engineer has no time to chase after trifles. In the complex physical objects that appear before his eyes, he must quickly find a point to which he can apply the mathematical tools given to him in his hands. How would he do it if there was that gap between objects and tools that logicians dug.

The current level of atmospheric pollution from exhaust emissions of the planet Earth is already excessively high, and a UN body called the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has ultimately determined a catastrophic increase in temperature on the planet by 2 ° C by

2036. In 2019, the journal Bioscience published an article prepared by the Alliance of World Scientists (AWS) titled "Global Scientists' Warning of a Climate

Emergency", stating in part that "We are clear and unequivocal that planet Earth is facing a climate emergency." climatic situation that threatens both natural

ecosystems and the fate of mankind. To ensure a sustainable future, we must change our way of life in ways that improve our interaction with natural ecosystems [Fig. 1]"

Figure 1. Planet Earth is facing a climate emergency

The lowering of the day surface, sometimes at a rate of tens of centimeters per year, not only increases the risk of flooding, flooding or swamping of territories, but can also cause deformation and damage to railways, roads, pipelines, bridges, residential buildings, and industrial enterprises. etc. Worst of all, all this, unlike global climate change, is a direct consequence of human activity. For example, the lowering of the relief is affected by the extraction of oil, gas and other minerals, loads from reservoirs, discharges into deposits, buildings and structures, garbage dumps, thawing of permafrost during ill-conceived construction on it, excessive pumping of groundwater from aquifers. At the same time, in terms of the frequency of manifestations, speed and negative consequences, the decrease in the surface level due to human fault exceeds natural processes.

The main global problem lies in the fact that mankind considers permanent pollution of the atmosphere with industrial emissions coming from the surface of the planet, mass epidemics and subsequent death of the population within the limited space of our existence in the lower layers of the troposphere as something distant.

The idea of saving the human race from extinction, expressed by Academician A.V. Kulakov, is the result of his 50 years of research in the field of breakthrough energy technologies in relation to the theory and practice of quantum nonlinear interactions of many particles. in non-ideal and close to degenerate plasma, as well as in condensed plasma media [1] – [4] [8]. This idea is of inexpressibly high value for all mankind, since it allows technologically to cope with the huge volumes of exhaust gases coming from the world industry and the huge amount of waste accumulated by the human race throughout its existence on planet Earth, through the implementation of the only one developed by the author in in the world of a clean energy system - nanoenergy of the Sixth Technological Order

[7], material fuel, for which there is literally the garbage of our planet and exhaust gases that destroy the health and immune system of the population, along with waste from industrial enterprises: sludge collectors, dumps of the mining industry and landfills for municipal solid waste. According to the newly proposed technology, the gases generated during the combustion of these wastes are not emitted into the atmosphere, but are fed into special sealed tanks equipped with devices developed by Academician A.V. Kulakov, which are used to obtain from the gas plasma under consideration (by compaction) an initially non-ideal plasma, and then, from the latter (through ionization), a new state of matter discovered by the author: a quantum plasma condensate, in which a phase transition occurs, accompanied by release of energy, the value of which exceeds the release of energy from the most economical types of fuel, with the exception of nuclear fuel materials. On the basis of the same technologies, gases emitted by the enterprises of the metallurgical and cement industries, enterprises for the processing of mining and energy raw materials, enterprises for the processing of nuclear waste, etc. can be processed.

The energy obtained by the technology developed by the author can be easily converted with an efficiency of 75% into thermal [6], electrical [5] or laser [8] energy. All of the above steps in the process of controlling the operation of power plants can be easily performed with experts in the field of physics. The work process was calculated by the author and described in previously published papers; it was verified by the author in the course of experiments carried out by him independently using the Universal Module of Industrial Disintegrators/Activators (UMID/A) developed by him [Fig. 2,3], where, for example, nanocement [7,10,11], the price of which was four times cheaper compared to the cements that existed at that time [Fig. 4] due to the absence of the annealing stage of the components in the technological process.

We list only some of the possible applications of UMTD/A:

The use of UMPD/A, in particular, is possible in the technology of obtaining cheap (four times cheaper than existing) highly durable alkaline nanocements resistant to sea water - without clinker firing, from local metallurgical slags, rocks and volcanic rocks;

UMPD/A, having remarkable structural properties, makes it possible to carry out large-scale construction using the 3D printing method, based on the use of a special water glass invented by us, obtained using cheap nanotechnology without sintering of components, which significantly increases the strength of concrete and wood concrete, and also allows to reduce the process by several times. "grasping";

It is important to use UMPD/A to improve the efficiency of oil cracking technologies and obtain cheap drilling fluids;

Coal ground in conventional mills to 50–100 μm is ground to a finely dispersed state in UMPD/A installations in water to obtain a high-quality, homogeneous, slightly settling suspension for effective use as boiler or furnace fuel for thermal power plants and cottages; When grinding coal or heavy fuel oils in diesel fuel, when selecting the appropriate concentration, cheap diesel fuel is obtained for use in powerful diesel engines of small power plants or powerful ship / mining diesel engines (mining dump trucks, tractors, bulldozers, excavators, as well as helicopters, cargo ships and port tugs);

It seems promising to use UMPD/A in the food industry: to obtain supersaturated solutions, caramel solutions, to obtain molasses from starch directly, without chemical hydrolysis, biological activation of water;

The water treated in UMPD/A does not scale in steam boilers, it has a reduced content of salts, heavy metals and dissolved gases, it is magnetized and an analogue of melt water. The UMPD/A technology should

be effectively used in the food industry as a churn and for the production of starch [15], margarine and mayonnaise, which is 200 times more efficient than ball mills in obtaining a suspension.

In total, about fifty new cheap nanotechnologies have been developed (of which more than ten are for the food industry), based on the use of patented UMPD/A.

We personally conducted a large number of experiments in cramped conditions on the UMPD/A built at our own expense, but with excellent results:

1. A new nanotechnological industrial method for producing ortho-silicic acid has been developed,

2. An industrial method for the manufacture of nano-cement has been developed.

Figure 8 demonstrates the possibility of obtaining, using the technology developed by us, nanocements from gypsum, rubble stone, coarse sand, kaolin and coal gold grinding - that is, fragile materials "rolling around underfoot", the use of which for these purposes was not previously possible. We list only some of the possible applications of UMTD/A:

Fundamentally new developed technology for processing waste thermoplastics and construction debris to obtain new harmless building materials is based on the unique technical capabilities of the developed Universal Module of Industrial Disintegrators/Activators. With the help of such modules, after pre-cooling and grinding in conventional mills, waste thermoplastics plastic bags, bottles, etc. are ground to the required tinting, blanked with fine graphite, warmed up and turned into slabs for paving streets. The resulting plates withstand the effects of any aggressive environments, low temperatures, do not absorb moisture, do not adsorb dirt and withstand technological and weather loads for more than 30 years

Rice. 2. Block UMM - 02. (Industrial disintegrators / activators (UMID / A))

 - Versatile multipurpose modules for continuous industrial grinding to nanopowder
 Rice. 3. Technological scheme of environmentally friendly waste processing technologies.

Rice. 4. Pilot samples of the final product of mining waste processing at the UMM-02 unit.

Therefore, in the case of introducing a source of clean energy - an environmentally friendly, cheap and most profitable one that has no competitors, since it is the only nature-like energy, efficient, renewable, renewable, inexpensive and sustainable nanoenergy In the Sixth Technological Order, which has no competitors due to its naturalness, pollution of all spheres of the planet Earth stops, and, consequently, global warming also stops, and the very use of this nanoenergy also becomes recycling. - the sector of processing and destruction of technogenic industrial and domestic waste accumulated by the planet Earth for the entire time of the existence of the latter. The use of new nanotechnologies and nanomaterials created in the course of the above studies will make it possible to mitigate the consequences of the economic crisis and recession associated [11,12], with the implementation of nanoenergy of the Sixth technological order, the fuel material for which is literally the waste of our planet and the exhaust gases are technologically simple and economically feasible: furnace designs are known, necessary for the incineration of industrial waste and garbage, and such furnaces are already in operation. In addition, when used for nanoenergy purposes, they become simpler in design and less expensive - there is no need to design flue gas treatment devices and install waste heat boilers. The processes of compaction and ionization of gases are described in the works published by the author. For the first time in world practice, we receive any of the known types of energy (thermal, electrical or laser) at

the output of devices used to convert exhaust gases and industrial waste.

Taking into account the relationship between air pollution with nitrogen dioxide and the mortality rate from the coronavirus COVID -19, revealed by researchers at the Martin Luther

University in Halle-Wittenberg, it can be assumed that the first countries that are able to relatively quickly and effectively implement (taking into account the cost-effective processes for creating energy nanogenerators) dreams of all mankind - the clean energy of nanoenergy of the Sixth technological order - could be small European countries with developed industry, science and medicine. science, countries that have realized that in this way the state can significantly (two to four times) increase state budget revenues, mitigate the effects of the economic crisis and recession and make the country's population more immune to infection. Nanoenergy of the sixth technological order free from the shortcomings of alternative "green" energy - its low energy intensity and efficiency, unresolved problems of utilization of wind energy components and the absolute vulnerability of solar and wind power plants from natural disasters/

Since the beginning of the 19th century, countries have switched to fuel combustion technologies with the release of heat-retaining gases into the atmosphere, with the Earth heating to date by 1.1 degrees Celsius. Scientists believe that only decisive action to reduce

emissions can keep the planet from exceeding 1.5 degrees of warming - a limit beyond which the consequences will become more catastrophic than rising sea levels, extreme weather. the goal is to achieve net zero emissions, the US by 2050, China by 2060, India by 2070 respectively, spending fantastic funds on this fix idea. Project Syndicate (USA): our future with zero greenhouse gas emissions

InoSMI

NEW YORK —« The solution to the man-made problem of climate change is finally clear. With the rapid development of technology in zero-carbon energy and sustainable food systems, the world can realistically end greenhouse gas emissions by mid-century, at little or no additional cost, and with huge security and health benefits. The main obstacle is inertia: politicians continue to pander to the fossil fuel industry and conventional agriculture, largely because they either don't know any better or because they are corrupt».

The way to achieve a clean climate is to replace existing obsolete technologies with the greatest achievement of mankind -Nanotechnology of a new technological a way of life that produces clean energy and cleanses the planet of human waste. But Science News «It is possible to achieve net zero carbon emissions. Here's how" , Alexandra Witze 27.01.2023."Such massive changes will require overcoming a lot of resistance, including from companies that make money on old forms of energy, as well as politicians, lobbyists" and I will add - the science mafia. But if society can make these changes, it will be one of the greatest achievements of mankind. We will solve the problem that we ourselves have created and overcome it.» However, it is necessary to take into account the opinions of the wisest people on the planet: Ravendra Nath Yasarapu commented on my work in the following way: «A beautifully laid out plan of action for energy and waste. But what to do with the primitive human instinct to hoard, compete, conflict and consume more than a fair share of the earth's resources? What if we are the enemy?» Maybe read a book about the planet Venus, from which not a single person was saved?

And, of course, I bow down, the deepest gratitude and recognition to my teachers, outstanding scientists, senior comrades and colleagues from past work, who have already passed away, to the President of the USSR Academy of Sciences Academician A.P. Alexandrov, Academician Nobel laureates in physics Prokhorov A.M. and Basov N.G. and Academician Nobel laureate in physics Zh.I. Alferov, who not only explained to me the scope of what I discovered in physics and what to do next, but also the features of my future fate: they told me: "Notice that a person who is ahead of his time is usually defenseless and is waiting for his arrival in uncomfortable conditions, surrounded by ill-wishers, in order to be a great scientist, you need to anticipate and remember for life the prophetic words of the great Russian scientist V.I. Vernadsky»:

"The whole history of science in each step shows what faces we more right in them statements than entire corporations of scientists or hundreds and thousands of

researchers adhering to to prevailing Views... Undoubtedly in our time he finds the truest, most correct and most profound scientific worldview among some individual scientists or small groups of researchers whose opinions do not attract our attention and cause us discontent or denial»l.

These instructions allowed me to withstand the blows of scientific fate and continue my scientific activity work.

AT my a heart, a Memory will always to be kept switched off my friend, a an excellent scientist and just a wise person,goctor of physical and mathematical sciences — Rumyantsev A.A.

References:

1. A.V. Kulakov, A.A. Rumyantsev. Spontaneous Plasma Magnetization of Quantum Origin , Journal of Technical Physics, 1988, Volume 58(4), pp. 657-660
2. Kulakov A.V., Orlenko E.V., Rumyantsev A.A. Quantum Exchange Forces in Condensed Matter, Moscow, Nauka Publishing House, 1990.
3. A.V. Kulakov, A.A. Rumyantsev. Ball lighting as a quantum condensate, Doklady AN SSSR, Fizika, 1991, vol. 1, p. 320(5) , p. 103-1106
4. A.V. Kulakov, V.A. Rantsev-Kartinov. Experimental confirmation of existence from plasma quantum condensate, News RAN. Energy, 2015 #1, pp. 46-61
5. average Kulakov. quantum plasma condensate How a new a source from electric energy. MHD - generator with plasma separation. International Journal of Advanced Studies, 2017, Volume 5(8), pp. 2004-2011.
6. AV Kulakov. Quantum non-ideal plasma as a source of thermal energy. Plasma Combustion of Fuel International Journal of Current Research, 2017, Vol . 9(6), pp. 5336153365
7. AV Kulakov. New modern nanoenergy. Fight against the coronavirus pandemic. Mitigation of the current crisis and fight against the global economic collapse. American Scientific Journal, 2020, No. 39, pp. 23-32
8. AV Kulakov. The new state of matter is a source of alternative renewable, harmless and efficient energy, the use of which restores the balance between the ecosphere and the technosphere. Magazine RadioFront , Vol . 02, pp. 2018, 48-54
9. A.V. Kulakov, V.A. Rantsev-Kartinov. Eurasian patent for invention No. 029979 Design of a universal module for industrial disintegrators/activators June 29, 2009 2018.
10. Kulakov A.V. Rantsev-Kartinov V.A. Application for Eurasian patent No. 201800299 for the invention "Method for producing nanocement ".
11. A.V. Kulakov, V.A. Rantsev-Kartinov. Proposals of new coal processing technologies based on the use of universal modules of industrial disintegrators/activators. American Scientific Journal, 2021, No. 50 pp.36-43.
12. A.V. Kulakov, V.A. Rantsev-Kartinov. New nanotechnologies for the production and use of hydrocarbons based on the use of universal disintegrators/activators. American scientific magazine . 2021, no. 50 p. 43-49.